

Symposium Classicum Peregrinum Lonato del Garda, Italy. 21-24 June, 2018

“Blessings and Curses in Antiquity”

Thursday 21 Lonato Castle

15.00 Greetings of the Mayor and of Patricia A. Johnston

Panel I. Curses in Context: Curse Tablets from Rome and Italy

Christopher A. Faraone, Introduction

Richard Gordon (Univ. Erfurt), “Do the Curse-Tablets from Italy Represent a Specific Knowledge-Practice?”

Raquel Martín Hernández (Complutense Univ., Madrid), “Eulamo or Seth?: On the Equineheaded God Represented in the *defixiones* from Rome”

Panel II: Curses and Blessings in the Roman World

Adrien Coignoux (Univ. Paris 7), “*Felicitas*: a Way to make Divine Interventions Obvious?”

Lorina Quartarone (Univ. of St. Thomas, Minnesota), “Dreams and Rituals: Subtle Inspirations in Aeneid 4”

Friday 22

9.00 Lonato Library. Session 1

Panel III: Curses in Context 3: Curse Tablets from the Latin West

Francisco Marco Simón (Univ. Zaragoza), “The Earliest Hispanic *Defixiones* and the Context of Some Iberian Texts Written on Lead”

Celia Sánchez Natalías (Univ. Zaragoza), “Aquatic Spaces as Contexts for depositing *defixiones* in the Roman West.”

Stuart Mckie (Univ. Manchester), “A Gift to the Gods by which Butu has perished...” Curse Tablets and Votive Rituals in the Roman North-West”

Roger Tomlin (Oxford Univ.), “The Latin Curses from Uley: Beyond the Interim Report”

György Nemeth (Univ. Budapest), “A Latin *Defixio* against Snakes and Scorpions from North-Africa”

15.00

Panel IV: Workshop on the Conservation and Photography of Lead Curse Tablets

Ida Ana Rapinesi (Soprintendenza Roma), “The Restoration of Magic Tablets from the Sanctuary of Anna Perenna”

Loretta Rossetti (Grand Patrimoine de Loire Atlantique, Laboratoire Arc Antique), “The Conservation of Lead Curse Tablets”

Mirco Cusin, Paul Gallo, and Stefano Magnani (Univ. Udine), “Reflection Transformation Imaging (RTI): Photographing Inscribed Curse Tablets (and *phylacteria*) and Producing Accurate Drawings of them”

Raquel Martín Hernández (Complutense Univ., Madrid): “New Technologies for Tracing Magical Drawings”

Saturday 23

9.00 Lonato Library. Session 1

Panel VI: Curse Tablets from the Italian Peninsula and Sardinia

Stefano Magnani (Univ. Udine), “Curse Tablets in the Wider Region of Aquileia”

Marina Piranomonte (Soprintendenza Roma), “New *defixiones* from Rome”

Riccardo Massarelli (Univ. Perugia), “The Etruscan *defixiones*: from Contexts to Texts”

Alessandra La Fragola (Univ. Almería), “The Ritual Context of the Curse Tablets from the La Purissima Sanctuary in Alghero, Sardinia”

Ciro Parodo (Univ. Cagliari), “The Celebration of the Lizard. Iconography and Meaning of an Apotropaic Ritual in Roman Late Antiquity”

Friday 22

9.00 Lonato Library. Session 2

Panel II: Curses and Blessings in the Roman World

Claudia Santi (Univ. Naples II), “Some Remarks on Latin Vocabulary of the Sacred: Augustum and Religiosum”

Victoria Györi (King’s College, London), “Augustus’ ‘Vota’ Coinage”

Francesca Ceci and Annarita Martini (Musei Capitolini, Rome), “The ‘Filatterio Capitolino’, the Greek-Jewish Lamella preserved in the Musei Capitolini: new Information concerning its Discovery”

Krešimir Vuković (British School Rome), “The Mystery lies within: Subterranean Spaces of the Forum and the Consecration of Marcus Curtius”

Gaius Stern, (Univ. California, Berkeley), “Devotio and Human Sacrifice in Archaic Italy and Rome”

Paolo Vitellozzi, (Univ. Perugia), “Binding Rituals in Italy: Greek Tradition and Autochthonous Contexts”

15.00

Panel II: Curses and Blessings in the Roman World

Nerea López Carrasco (Univ. Malaga), “Comparison and Reflection on two Formulas for Consecration: Greek $\kappa\alpha\theta\iota\epsilon\rho\acute{o}\omega$ ($\tau\acute{\omega}$ $\theta\epsilon\acute{\omega}$) and Latin *sacer* (*deo*)”

Danuta Musiał (Nicolaus Copernicus Univ., Toruń) and **Andrzej Gillmeister** (Univ. of Zielona Góra), “Evocatio deorum as the Example of the Crisis Ritual in Roman Religion”

Nicolas Corre (Univ. Rennes), “Between the Pure and the Impure: The Particular Case of the Homo Sacer”

Attilio Mastrocinque, (Univ. Verona), “The Roman *consecratio* as a public curse”

Henry Walker (Bates College, Maine), “The Good, the Bad, and the Holy, from the Republic to the Empire”

Alain Blomart (Univ. Barcelona), “Evocatio and devotio: From the Religious Ritual to Roman Law”

Saturday 23

9.00 Lonato Library. Session 2

Panel VII: Religions Dominated by Mothering Women: Unveiling Dynamics and Emotions in Religious Practices Involving Children in Danger, Mothers, and Mother-like Figures in Ancient Italy

Claudia Lambrugo (Univ. Milan), “The Power of *keimelia*. Protecting Children with Ancient Stones”

Giulia Pedrucci (Univ. Erfurt), “Who protects the Children in Roman Religion? From whom? Some Reflections concerning Carna and Thesan”

Michaela Kellová (Charles Univ. of Prague), “Who is His Mother so I can Curse Him?”

Nadia Pezzulla (Univ. Roma), “Children, Health, and Death, and the Relationship between Mother and Child in the Ancient Near-East.”

Saturday 23. Session 1

Romina Carboni, (Univ. Cagliari), “A Case Study of Magic and *maleficia* in the Ancient World: The Roman Sardinia”

15.00

Panel V: Curses and Blessings in the Greek World

Emiliano Cruccas (Univ. Cagliari), “Blessings for the Sailors. the Cult of The Great Gods of Samothrace in the Mediterranean Context between Hellenistic and Roman Age”

Alexandre Jakubiec (ENS Lyon), “A New Way of Understanding the Relationship between Men and the Gods: Socrates, Gods and Wealth”

Dan-Tudor Ionescu (Metrop. Library Bucharest), “The Celtic Oath and the Celts’. Worst Fear in the Encounter with Alexander the Great on the Danube in 335 BC”

Chiara Di Serio, (Univ. Roma), “Signs and Premonitions for Alexander’s Kingdom”

Daniel Sarefield (Fitchburg Univ.), ““To the Ravens’: Curses from the Oracle of Abonouteichos”

Aurelio Pérez Jiménez (Univ. Málaga), “The Unarmed Gods: Astral Implications on Certain Blessing and Curse Formulas”

Anna J. Tóth (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest), “The Suppliant and the Demons in the *lex sacra* of Cyrene”

Diego Romagnoli (Accad. Marchigiana), “*Benevolentia et malevolentia deorum* in Mithraic, Magical and Theurgic Rites”

Sunday 24

9.00 Lonato Library (or at the Roman kilns)

Panel VIII: Games, Fate and Chance (ERC AdvG Locus Ludi)

Salvatore Costanza (Univ. Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi), “Aphrodite playing Astragali: Erotic Oracles and Invocations to Venus in Astragalomancy”

Véronique Dassen, (Univ. Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi), “Games, Fate and Chance”

Fabio Spadini (Univ. Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi), “Playing with Fate: Horoscopes and Engraved Gemstones”

Marco Vespa (Univ. Fribourg/ERC Locus Ludi), “Taken by the Hair: an Introduction into Chance and Fortune in Ancient Greece”

Journey to Sirmione and the Roman villa

The Symposium is organized by Patricia Johnston, Christopher Faraone, Attilio Mastrocinque, László Takács, and Elisa Zentilini info: elisa.zentilini@gmail.com

